

1 *Original Article*2 **Pattern of the Medical Emergencies seen in the Accident and Emergency Department of Barau Dikko Teaching**
3 **Hospital, Kaduna. North-western Nigeria. 2022**4 Sani H¹, Yakubu P.D¹ Mahmood D¹, Bello-ovosi B¹, Sadauki H A², Abubakar A.B^{1*}

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7 * Correspondence: dizalng@yahoo.com; Tel.: +2348036784444(Sani Hadiza)8 **Abstract:**9 **Background**

10 Medical emergencies are acute illnesses that require immediate assistance or intervention from a qualified personnel¹. Outcome of these
11 emergencies depend on the location, health care system, and trained personnel's amongst others. Studies have shown that no two facilities have
12 the same pattern of diseases and no single facility will have the same findings at different times^{3,4}.

13 We conducted a descriptive cross-sectional study to evaluate the pattern and outcomes of medical admissions into the accident and emergency
14 room of Barau Dikko Teaching Hospital, Kaduna State.

15 **Methodology**

16 This was a retrospective study carried out from January to December 2022. Patients' data were extracted from the EMR on to an Excel sheet

17 **Citation:** Authors First and Initials after obtaining ethical approval. Categorical data was summarised using frequencies and percentages. The

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relationship between variables was examined using odds ratio. A p-value of <0.05 was considered
statistically significant.

20 **Results**

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23 causes (82.0%) of medical emergency admissions were non-communicable diseases, of which

A total of 889 patients with male:female ratio of 1.01:1.00 and mean age of 43.4 (±18.9) years were seen in
2022. Those less than 45 years accounted for more than half (53.3%) of the admission. The most common
causes (82.0%) of medical emergency admissions were non-communicable diseases, of which

24 cardiovascular disorders were the most prominent (16.6%), followed by neurological emergencies (14.8%) and haematologic emergencies
25 (14.6%). Among the communicable diseases, Sepsis (16%) was the most common cause of admissions. A higher proportion of women had
26 cardiovascular and respiratory emergencies while the men had chronic liver diseases and upper gastrointestinal bleeding ($P < 0.01$). Acute liver
27 failure, leukaemias, Gullain-Barre syndrome, Pericardial effusions with tamponade as well as acute pulmonary embolism have the highest case
28 fatality rate of 100%.

29 **Conclusion**

30 The higher prevalence of non-communicable diseases in this study suggest epidemic transition from communicable to non-communicable
31 diseases, hence the need to strengthen health education and life style modifications in order to reduce the burden of these diseases.

32 Key words- Medical emergencies, Kaduna, North-western Nigeria

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35 **1. Introduction**

36 The capacity of the health system to promptly detect and effectively manage
37 emergencies provide an insight into the overall functionality of the health system.
38 Periodic reviews of the pattern of admissions and outcomes of individual facilities is an
39 essential monitoring and evaluation tool needed for system improvement. More so, the
40 changing demographics as well as the ongoing epidemiological transition in developing
41 countries makes regular evaluations more compelling. A careful review of the several
42 efforts to explore patterns and outcomes of admissions into the emergency rooms in
43 Nigerian tertiary facilities revealed that no two facilities have the same findings and no
44 single facility will have the same findings at different times ^{3,4} . While some studies
45 revealed the predominance of infectious diseases, others, in keeping with the ongoing
46 epidemiologic transition, has shown the increasing relevance of non-communicable
47 diseases ¹⁻⁴ . Finally, the recent introduction of electronic medical records in our
48 healthcare facilities also calls for exploration of the effectiveness of the archival system
49 and its utility for enabling collation of and utilization of the databases generated
50 therefrom. The aim of this study is to find out the pattern of medical and outcome of
51 medical emergencies in Barau Dikko Teaching Hospital, Kaduna and factors associated
52 with outcome.

53 **Study design**

54 A retrospective cross sectional study.

55 **Study area**

56 Barau Dikko Teaching Hospital (BDTH) is the one of the tertiary facilities in Kaduna North-western Nigeria named
57 after the first medical doctor in the north – Dr. Russell Barau Dikko. It is located at Unguwar Rimi, Kaduna North

58 Local Government, at Coordinate: Longitude 7.44228 and Latitude 7.44228. It was established in 1930 during the
 59 colonial era to serve the colonial masters and their family. Subsequently, it was upgraded to a teaching hospital in
 60 2016 after successful accreditation by both the National Universities Commission (NUC) and the Medical and Dental
 61 Council of Nigeria (MDCN). The 300-bedded facility receive referrals from all the primary and secondary facilities
 62 in the state. It has a 44-bedded Accident and Emergency (A & E) Department where medical emergencies are triaged,
 63 resuscitated, and discharged home or are assigned to appropriate teams for further evaluation and specialist care.
 64 Patients are admitted in the A and E for 24-48 hours before transfer to the either the medical or surgical wards. Since
 65 January 2020, patients' records have been managed using an Electronic Medical Records (EMR) system.

66 Data collection and analysis

67 Patients' data were extracted from the EMR on to an Excel sheet after obtaining ethical approval. The study covered a
 68 period of twelve months between January to December 2022. Incomplete data and surgical cases were excluded.
 69 Variables like age, sex, date and time of admission, diagnosis, duration of stay and outcome (discharged, dead,
 70 referred) were exported into Epi Info Version 7.2.5.0 for analysis. Categorical data was summarised using frequencies
 71 and percentages. Numerical data was summarised using appropriate measures of central tendency. Data was
 72 presented in tables and charts. The relationship between outcome (dead/discharged or transferred) and patient
 73 characteristics was examined using odds ratio with 95% confidence interval. Variables with a P-value of ≤ 0.2 on
 74 bivariate analysis were entered into a multivariate regression model to adjust for confounding and calculate adjusted
 75 odds ratios. A P-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

76 Results

77 A total of 889 patients were seen in 2022. The median (range) age (years) was 42 (3 - 102). More than half of the
 78 patients 474/881 (53.3) were < 45 years. There were 448/889 (50.4%) males and 441/889 females with a M:F ratio of
 79 1.01:1. Majority of the patients 481/889 (54.1%) belonged to the Hausa ethnic group (Table 1).

80 Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of medical emergencies in BDTH, Kaduna, Nigeria, 2022

Characteristic	Male Frequency (%)	Female Frequency (%)	Total Frequency (%)
Age Group			
<45 years	249 (52.5)	225 (47.5)	474 (53.3)
45 - 65 years	118 (45.0)	144 (55.0)	262 (29.5)
>65 years	79 (54.5)	66 (45.5)	145 (16.3)
Total	446 (50.6)	435 (49.4)	881 (99.1)
Ethnicity			
Hausa	238 (49.5)	243 (50.5)	481 (54.1)
Yoruba	18 (46.2)	21 (53.8)	39 (4.4)
Igbo	14 (53.8)	12 (46.2)	26 (2.9)
Others	178 (51.9)	165 (48.1)	343 (38.5)

81 Total 448 (50.4%) 441 (49.6%) 889 (100)

82

83 The most frequent cause of A&E admission was non-communicable diseases (NCD) accounting for 725/889 (81.6%).
 84 Cardiovascular disorders were the most common NCD accounting for 148/889 (16.6%) of the total admissions.
 85 Communicable/infectious diseases accounted for 134/889 (15.1%) of medical emergencies. Sepsis was the commonest
 86 communicable disease diagnosis accounting for 34/880 (3.8%) of medical emergencies.
 87 Table 2 shows the distribution of the medical emergencies by gender. A significantly higher proportion of women had
 88 cardiovascular ($P < 0.01$) and respiratory emergencies.

89 Diseases	Frequency Sex (M/F)	Total
90 Infectious diseases	76/84	160
91 Cardiovascular emergencies	57/91	148
92 Gastroenteric emergencies	74/59	133
93 Neurological	70/62	132
94 Heamatologic emergencies	80/50	130
95 Renal emergencies	37/24	61
96 Endocrine emergencies	22/27	49
97 Respiratory emergencies	13/26	39
98 Poisons/bites	12/16	28
99 Dermatology	5/2	07
100 Psychiatry	1/1	02
101 Total	447/442	889

102
 103 A higher number of medical emergencies were managed during the second half of the year with the month of August
 104 having the highest of 138/889 (15.5%). The monthly trend in the medical emergencies seen is shown in Figure 1. The
 105 proportion of admissions that resulted in mortality is represented by the orange line in Figure 1. The highest
 106 proportion of mortality occurred in September where 26/95 (27.4%) of admissions resulted in mortality.
 107 Figure 1. Shows monthly trend in admissions and mortality.

108
 109 The median (IQR) duration of stay was 12 days (2 hours - 8 days). Following treatment, 505/889 (56.8%) patients were
 110 discharged, 39/889 patients (4.4%) were discharged against medical advice, 21/889 (2.4%) were referred to other
 111 facilities, and 169/889 (19.0%) were not documented. Among the deaths, there were

112 94/169 (55.6%) males. The commonest cause of death was non-communicable diseases, which accounted for 132/169
 113 (78.1%) fatalities; among these, stroke accounted for the greatest number with 47/169 patients (27.8%). Sepsis topped
 114 the list of communicable disease fatalities with 14/169 patients (8.3%) (Table 3). Case fatalities for Guillan Barre
 115 Syndrome (GBS), acute liver failure, leukaemia and pulmonary embolism were 100% (Table 3). The age specific
 116 mortality rates for all causes for patients aged < 45 years was 63/326 (19.3%), for patients aged 45 - 65 years it was
 117 66/163 (40.4%) and for patients aged > 65 years it was 39/70 (55.7%)

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120 Table 3: Case fatality rates of medical emergencies in BDTH Kaduna, Nigeria, 2022.

Diseases	Frequency (n = 610)	Number of deaths	Case fatality
Cardiovascular			
Cardiogenic shock	3	2	66.7%
Heart failure	46	9	19.6%
Hypertensive Emergency	65	3	4.6%
Myocardial Infarction	6	1	16.7%
Pericardial disease	2	2	100.0%
Endocrine			
Hyperglycaemia	33	4	12.1%
Hypoglycaemia	6	3	50.0%
Gastroenterology			
Acute liver failure	2	2	100.0%
Acute gastroenteritis	24	2	8.3%
Chronic liver disease	43	22	51.2%
Hepato-cellular carcinoma	4	1	25.0%
UGIB	14	4	28.6%
Haematological			
Anaemia	8	3	37.5%
Leukaemia	1	1	100.0%
Malignancy	5	2	40.0%
SCA	97	3	3.0%
Infectious diseases			
HIV	13	7	53.8%
Severe malaria	24	5	20.8%
Meningitis	3	3	100.0%
Pneumonia	5	1	20.0%
Pyelonephritis	7	1	11.1%
Sepsis	26	14	14.3%
Tuberculosis	13	4	30.8%
Nephrology			
AKI	8	4	50.0%
CKD	38	11	28.9%

Dialysis complication	2	1	50.0%
Neurology			
GBS	1	1	100.0%
Seizure disorder	6	1	16.6%
SOL	1	1	100.0%
Stroke	76	47	61.8%
Respiratory			
Cor pulmonale	3	2	66.7%
Pulmonary embolism	1	1	100.0%
Bites/poisonings	24	1	4.2%
Total	610	169	27.7%

121

122 Patients with stroke, HIV-related complications, severe sepsis, diabetic hypoglycaemic emergencies, and chronic liver
 123 disease had higher odds for mortality. Patients who stayed ≤ 48 hours had twice the odds for mortality than patients
 124 who were admitted for > 48 hours. Patients with sickle cell-related complications had lower odds for mortality. Age
 125 and sex were not associated with mortality. (Table 4).

126 Table 4 Predictors of mortality among emergency medical cases in Barau Dikko Teaching Hospital Kaduna, Nigeria,
 127 2022

Characteristic	Outcome		OR (95% C. I.)	P-value	AOR (95% C. I.)
	Dead (%) n = 169	Discharged/ referred (%) n = 565			
Sex					
Male	94 (55.6)	277 (49.0)	1.3 (0.9 - 1.8)	0.132	1.2 (0.8 – 1.8)
Female	75	288	1		
Age					
> 65 years	39 (23.2)	70 (12.5)	2.9 (1.8 - 4.6)	<0.001	1.2 (0.6 - 2.1)
45 - 65 years	66 (39.2)	163 (29.2)	2.1 (1.4 - 3.1)	<0.001	1.1 (0.7 - 1.8)
< 45 years	63 (37.5)	326 (58.3)	1		
Time of admission					
Working hours	124 (73.4)	379 (67.4)	1.9 (0.9 - 2.0)	0.144	1.1 (0.7 -1.5)
Call hours	45	183	1		
Diagnosis					
Stroke	47 (27.8)	29 (5.1)	7.1 (4.3 - 11.8)	<0.001	9.4 (5.2 – 17.3)
Others	122	536	1		
Diagnosis					
Heart failure	9 (5.3)	37 (6.6)	0.8 (0.4 - 1.7)	0.565	-
Other	160	528	1		
Diagnosis					
HIV	7 (4.1)	6 (1.1)	4.7 (1.3 -12.1)	0.008	9.3 (2.9 – 29.8)
Others	162	559	1		
Diagnosis					

Characteristic	Outcome		OR (95% C. I.)	P-value	AOR (95% C. I.)
	Dead (%) n = 169	Discharged/ referred (%) n = 565			
Sepsis	14 (8.3)	12 (2.1)	4.2 (1.9 - 9.2)	<0.001	8.0 (3.3 - 19.3)
Others	155	553	1		
Diagnosis					
CLD	23 (13.6)	24 (4.3)	3.6 (1.9 - 6.5)	<0.001	6.8 (3.4 - 13.6)
Other	146	541			
Diagnosis					
Acute gastroenteritis	2 (1.2)	22 (3.9)	0.3 (0.1 - 1.3)	0.082	0.5 (0.1 - 2.0)
Others	167		1		
Diagnosis					
AKI	4 (2.4)	4 (0.7)	3.4 (0.8 - 13.7)	0.068	5.6 (1.3 - 24.0)
Others	165	561	1		
Diagnosis					
CKD	11 (6.5)	27 (4.8)	1.4 (0.7 - 2.9)	0.373	-
Other	158	538	1		
Diagnosis					
Hyperglycaemic emergency	4 (2.4)	29 (5.1)	0.4 (0.2 - 1.3)	0.128	9.5 (0.3 - 2.9)
Other	165	536	1		
Diagnosis					
Hypoglycaemic emergency	3 (1.8)	3 (0.5)	3.4 (0.7 - 16.9)	0.115	6.9 (1.2 - 38.2)
Other	166	562	1		
Diagnosis					
SCA	3 (1.8)	94 (16.6)	0.09 (0.02 - 0.29)	<0.001	0.2 (0.1 - 0.8)
Other	166	471	1		
Duration of stay					
≤ 48 hours	98 (58.0)	237 (41.0)	1.9 (1.3 - 2.7)	<0.001	2.3 (1.5 - 3.4)
> 48 hours	71	328	1		

128

129 **Discussion**

130 Medical emergencies vary from one community to another and the pattern of presentations can be used to prioritize
131 resources and assist in health care planning.

132 This study shows a high incidence of non-communicable diseases especially cardiovascular emergencies being the
133 indication for admissions while stroke and sepsis were the major causes of mortality.

134 The mean age of the patients 43.4 (\pm 18.9) in this study is similar to mean ages observed in Zaria (44.17), Port-Harcourt
135 (45.50) and Kano (40.30) 5-7. However, in a study by Deepak et al in India⁸, he found a mean age of (28.6) 9. The lower
136 mean age reported in the latter may be due to the enrolment of children less than 10 years of age in their study.

137 There was an almost equal M:F of 1.01:1. Previous reported findings within and outside the country have quoted
138 similar ratios of 0.99:16,1.2:17, 1.1:18, 1.2:19. This may indicate an equal burden of diseases in both genders.

139 More than half (54.1%) of the respondents were of Hausa ethnicity. It was not surprising that most of the patients
140 were of Hausa ethnic group because they constitute the major ethnic group in North-western Nigeria.

141 Young people less than 45 years constituted the bulk of admission (53.3%) this was closely followed by the middle
142 aged 45-65 years (29.5%). Table 1. Previous studies have shown similar age group forming the bulk of
143 admissions.^{1,3,4-7} This age group are the productive and reproductive age and with these trends in presentation,
144 there may be increase morbidity and mortality which may adversely affect life expectancy, economic growth and
145 development.

146 The most frequent causes of presentation/admission were non-communicable diseases (NCD) accounting for (81.6%)
147 of the admissions with cardiovascular diseases (heart failure and hypertensive crises) forming (16.6%), this was
148 closely followed by neurological emergencies (stroke) (14.8%), haematological emergencies (sickle cell emergencies)
149 (14.6%) and Gastroenteric emergencies CLD and PUD (17.9%). NCDs have been on the rise recently as other studies
150 in the country have shown. ^{5,6,9,11-16}.

151 Although NCDs were higher than infectious emergencies in our study (81.6%:15.1%), studies done in other centres
152 with similar picture have quoted lower ratios (78.2:21.8%)². The lower values of NCD seen in the latter study by Ogah
153 et al (2012) may be due to the time interval between the two studies coupled with the western life styles being
154 adopted and urbanization. NCDs are expected to account for more than 50% of deaths by 2030 in Sub-Saharan
155 Africa.¹⁷

156 It is worthy of note that more women had cardiovascular and respiratory emergencies and this was statistically
157 significant ($P < 0.01$) while a higher proportion of men had decompensated liver disease ($P < 0.01$) and upper
158 gastro-intestinal bleeding (UGIB) ($P < 0.01$) see table 2.

159 The most common neurological emergencies seen was stroke forming 11.5% of the total emergencies. Other
160 emergencies were renal (CKD) 5.2%, respiratory (acute severe asthma) 3.1%, haematology (sickle cell crises) 3.1% and
161 poisoning/bites (substance abuse and animal bites) 3.1%.

162 Infectious emergencies constituted 15.1% of the total emergencies with sepsis, severe malaria and tuberculosis
163 forming 3.8%, 3.6% and 2.1% respectively. HIV related diseases accounted for 1.8% of the total admission. Previous
164 studies have shown higher levels of infections and HIV related diseases 38.8%³, 34.1%⁵, 21.8%⁶, 35.1%¹⁰, 67.4%¹¹,
165 47.6%¹²

166 The low figures seen in this study may due to the improved sanitation, immunization and an efficient and
167 patient-friendly HIV clinic established in the centre.

168 Severe malaria is still seen in our environment and most of the patients had used different forms of artemisinin-based
169 combination (ATC) before presentation. This may due to re-emergence of resistance to ACT based combinations.¹⁸
170 Similarly, most of the cases of tuberculosis observed in this study were more of extrapulmonary forms with pleural
171 effusion requiring chest tube insertions.

172 A higher number of medical emergencies were managed during the second half of the year with the month of August
173 having the highest of 138/889 (15.5%). See Figure 1. This is usually a peak period of rain. This finding may be due to
174 the associated immunological reaction to seasonal changes. Similar findings have been recorded by different studies
175 across the country^{3,5,19}. Records of several years will need to be studied to ascertain this trend so as to prepare for the
176 high influx during this period.

177 The median duration of stay was 12 days (2 hours-8 days) this includes those transferred to the ward and their
178 duration of stay. More than half of the patients were discharged 56.8%, 19% died, about 4.4% left against medical

advice, 2.4% were referred to other facilities. Outcome of 17.4% of the cases was not documented, this accounted for the incomplete/missing data. This may not be unrelated to poorly saved data or frequent power outages.

Amongst the deaths recorded during the period under review, 55.6% were males this is also similar to studies in Port-Harcourt²⁰ and Owerri²¹. This may be due to the fact that there were more males than females in this study and men, generally are likely to withstand chronic illness and present acutely when diseases are advanced, similarly the male gender are said to have a higher tendency to developing strokes, kidney disease and hypertension.²²⁻²⁴

Non communicable diseases (NCDs) accounted for 78.1% of mortalities with stroke (27.8%), Decompensated CLD (13%), and Sepsis (8.3%), being the major contributors to mortality.

Overall mortality from all the medical emergencies was 19%, this is higher than previous studies in different centres –9.7%⁶, 11.4%¹⁰. The high mortality seen in this study may be due to poor level of development and inadequate trained man-power.

All those who had Guillan-Barre syndrome, acute liver failure, leukaemia and pulmonary embolism died following admission giving a case fatality of 100%. (Table 3). These conditions usually present in severe acute forms or in advanced stages of decompensation where not much can be done especially in resource poor settings like ours.

The age specific mortality rates for all causes for patients aged < 45 years was 63/326 (19.3%), 45 - 65 years was 66/163 (40.4%) and for those > 65 years was 39/70 (55.7%). It is worthy of note that elderly have a higher chance of dying following presentation.

Patients with stroke, HIV-related complications, severe sepsis, diabetic hypoglycaemic emergencies, and chronic liver disease had higher odds for mortality, the need for a stroke unit, intensification of HIV control programme, health education, life style modification and improved vaccination for prevention viral hepatitis respectively cannot be over emphasized. Those who stayed ≤ 48 hours had twice the odds for mortality than patients who were admitted for > 48 hours. Patients with sickle cell-related complications had lower odds for mortality. Age and sex were not associated with mortality. (Table 4).

Conclusion

The higher prevalence of non-communicable diseases in this study suggest epidemic transition from communicable to non-communicable diseases with cardiovascular and neurological diseases accounting for the majority of admissions while stroke and sepsis were the top causes of mortality.

Conflicts of Interest - The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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Authors' Contributions

Hadiza Sani - Conceptualization, writing of manuscript, data collection

Yakubu P.D – Data collection, review of manuscript

Dalhat Mahmood – Conceptualization, input of data and analysis of data

Bello-Ovosi B – Input of data, review of manuscript

Sadauki H A – Input of data and analysis, review of manuscript

Abubakar A.B – Review of manuscript, study design

All authors approved the final copy of the manuscript

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